

Distrusting cores by separating computation from isolation

Nils Asmussen*, Till Miemietz, Sebastian Haas, Michael Roitzsch

Barkhausen Institut, Schweriner Straße 1, Dresden, 01067, Germany

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Multicore architectures
Hardware security
Reliability
Operating systems

ABSTRACT

Security mechanisms such as address spaces rely on the assumption that processor cores can be fully trusted. But the steady influx of side-channel vulnerabilities in processors is challenging this assumption. To minimize the impact of security vulnerabilities in processors, we need a system architecture that can tolerate potentially exploitable cores.

In this paper, we propose the *untrusted core isolation* model to protect critical computation on trusted cores from untrusted and potentially buggy cores. We survey how current architectural building blocks such as MMUs fall short of this goal and derive requirements for untrusted core isolation. To demonstrate its feasibility, we discuss both changes to commodity platforms and show how research works such as M³ fulfill the requirements. We evaluate the security benefits via a qualitative comparison of current architectures in both industry and academia and study its costs by a quantitative comparison of the most promising approaches on off-the-shelf and FPGA-based platforms.

1. Introduction

Processor-level vulnerabilities such as Spectre [1], Meltdown [2], and \AA PIC [3] have shown the isolation limits on high-performance out-of-order processors. Research regularly uncovers new variants [4–10] and there are studies [11] indicating that this class of hardware security vulnerabilities is here to stay.

Such weaknesses are problematic for use cases where strong isolation is of paramount importance, like customer separation in cloud computing and service separation in cyber–physical systems. Cloud providers want to provision machines with many processor cores and then rent portions of these machines to customers. The groups of cores for an individual customer must be strongly separated from the cores of another customer. Particularly, any kind of data leakage must be prevented, otherwise trust in the business model may diminish. Cyber-physical systems such as cars or medical devices require a related but different kind of separation. These systems use heterogeneous cores to run code with different reliability requirements [12,13]. A fast and complex core runs convenience functionality on a general-purpose system. Safety-critical or real-time tasks run on cores with reduced complexity to increase reliability. However, without proper isolation between those cores, the safety-critical task still relies on the correctness of the complex core, reducing overall reliability to the least reliable core.

Current mitigation options for processor-level vulnerabilities range from scheduling techniques [14], compiler techniques [15], software

architectures [11], kernel-level mitigations [16], firmware updates, and hardware modifications. With such a variety of techniques, reasoning about isolation is challenging and calls for an easier abstraction.

In this paper, we want to take the extreme position of assuming that individual cores can be fully compromised with regard to their isolation features, including user code exercising full read and write access to kernel code by somehow bypassing memory protection. Although Meltdown only offered a kernel-read primitive, we want to explore this extreme assumption to protect against more severe future discoveries. It is already common today to assume that accelerators and I/O devices are potentially broken. We also see this assumption supported by industry solutions such as Apple SEP [17] or AMD PSP [18], which introduce a completely isolated core for security reasons. We also believe that an architecture that can tolerate broken cores can help to protect critical computations from soft errors caused by radiation or silicon decay. Note that we use the term *broken* in this paper when referring to cores that contain any unintentional or intentional bug that allows to compromise the security of the system (e.g., leak information, manipulate data, or corrupt data).

Given this assumption, we want to implement *untrusted core isolation* (UCI) with the goal to shield trusted cores from the influence of untrustworthy cores and thereby provide an easy abstraction to reason about isolation. We analyze candidate architectures regarding the components that need to be trusted for isolation enforcement and

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: nils.asmussen@barkhauseninstitut.org (N. Asmussen), till.miemietz@barkhauseninstitut.org (T. Miemietz), sebastian.haas@barkhauseninstitut.org (S. Haas), michael.roitzsch@barkhauseninstitut.org (M. Roitzsch).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sysarc.2024.103328>

Received 12 June 2024; Received in revised form 18 November 2024; Accepted 8 December 2024

Available online 18 December 2024

1383-7621/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

management. This set of components must not overlap with the set of cores we do not want to trust. Regarding isolation, we must look at all communication channels leaving a core, which include memory and device buses but also messaging channels such as interrupts or cache coherence. Any of these channels could be used by an untrusted core to cross a trust boundary and influence a core we need to trust. We discuss the goals of UCI, the trusted computing base, and the attacker model in more detail in Section 2.

In Section 3, we survey candidate architectures according to the UCI goals. We construct candidates systematically from existing architectural building blocks such as MMUs to explore what can be achieved with off-the-shelf components. MMUs implement isolation enforcement for memory accesses, but we must consider the management aspect as well. One important lesson therefore is that the traditional solution of running an operating system kernel across all cores in a privileged processor mode leads to architectures where all cores must be fully trusted. As we identify their shortcomings, we derive requirements from all our candidate solutions. Our spectrum of candidates ranges from typical commodity systems over datacenter-inspired network-based isolation to IOMMU-based approaches from safety-critical embedded platforms.

From the derived requirements, we extrapolate in Section 4, what a clean-slate redesign looks like. Ideally, the primary and sole responsibility of a core is to compute, while components external to the core are responsible for inter-core isolation. With M^3 [19], we identify a research architecture that closely implements this ideal. Existing research on M^3 already studied different aspects of this system architecture, starting from the general architecture [19], followed by the integration of accelerators [20] and core multiplexing [21] and finally about its real-time properties [22]. However, this paper is the first to study how this approach can be used to integrate arbitrarily broken cores into a system.

In summary, this paper makes the following contributions: (1) We introduce UCI as a model to evaluate architectures with the goal of distrusting entire cores. (2) We survey candidate architectures using existing off-the-shelf building blocks (SGX, MMUs, IOMMUs, IPs, NICs, SR-IOV). From the shortcomings of these candidates we derive requirements for UCI. (3) Based on these requirements we conduct a clean-slate redesign and analyze M^3 as a fitting research system. (4) We evaluate the closest fitting candidate architectures against M^3 using cloud and IoT workloads to demonstrate the security and performance benefits of enforcement/management co-design for untrusted core isolation.

2. Untrusted core isolation

To motivate our work, we begin with a look on the recent processor vulnerabilities and why we think they cannot simply be fixed. We continue with the goals of the untrusted core isolation model and explain the trusted computing base as well as our attacker model.

2.1. Motivation

Hardware-based side-channel attacks are not a new phenomenon. Cache-based side channels have been investigated for years, but they were considered problematic only for niches such as cryptographic software [23–25], because this software handles very few very precious bits. This viewpoint shifted with Spectre [1] and Meltdown [2] in 2018, when cache-based side channels were combined with speculative execution to extract micro-architectural state that should never be architecturally visible. In the case of Meltdown, this side-channel completely bypassed kernel protection and enabled user-mode code to read arbitrary kernel memory. Similarly, Spectre allowed data extraction across protection boundaries.

As researchers targeted other micro-architectural features, many similar problems were discovered in rapid succession [4–8,10]. Short

term mitigations were developed but come with noticeable performance costs [26]. Ultimately, the root causes need to be addressed in hardware, raising the question, whether these problems demand us to rethink our architecture or whether we can simply go ahead and fix all these vulnerabilities. We believe the ‘just fix’ position is indefensible for two reasons. First, studies have demonstrated that it is infeasible to find all these hardware issues systematically [27]. Spectre and related side-channel vulnerabilities are here to stay [11], because speculative execution is fundamentally susceptible to such side channels. Second, the overarching problem is the enormous growth in core complexity over the years [28], resulting not only in speculation-based side channels but also other unwanted feature interactions like recently demonstrated by the $\text{\AE}P\text{IC}$ Leak [3]. Furthermore, GhostWrite [29] has recently demonstrated that vulnerabilities are not limited to data leaks, but can also provide attackers write access to the whole system memory.

This feature complexity of modern cores is thus at the heart of the problem. However, it is also necessary for growth in compute performance since Dennard scaling [30] has ended. Additional core performance is no longer achieved by increased frequency, but by speculation, instruction optimizations, and specialized accelerators, all of which add to the complexity of the core. Outside of niche applications, where security requirements may dictate a custom-tailored low-complexity core, we do not want to give up performance. We therefore do not advocate against this trend.

However, we do advocate for managing the resulting complexity differently. In the software domain, it is accepted wisdom that reasonably complex software will contain bugs, but systems are structured in a way to tolerate these bugs. Microkernels [31–33] for example employ fine-grained segregation between system components such as device drivers and file systems in order to contain the faults that will invariably occur. It has been shown that microkernels could have reduced the severity or completely prevented 96% of the exploits in Linux [34]. We suggest to apply the same mindset of rigorous core isolation to hardware architectures in order to tolerate vulnerable cores.

In this paper, we take the hypothetical position, that cores can be arbitrarily broken and set out to construct a system architecture around this assumption. We see this position supported by current industry solutions such as Apple SEP [17] or AMD PSP [18], which introduce a completely isolated core for security reasons. This step makes sense, if there is a chance that the main core fails to protect its secrets.

2.2. Goals

Untrusted core isolation (UCI) has the goal to enforce separation between cores running multiple distrusting software components. These components could represent software run by different cloud customers or tasks on a cyber-physical device with different reliability requirements. Software component A should only have to trust its own core for its correct operation, but should not need to trust the core hosting software component B. Instead, A should be protected by architectural features from malicious influence from B’s core. This protection should not rely on the core restricting itself but must be externally enforced.

We rule out trivial solutions, where components A and B are fully air-gapped. Communication between them must still be possible, but UCI must ensure that all communication channels leaving a core must be policed before reaching another core. These channels are: *memory accesses* including cache coherence, *signaling* via interrupts or message passing, as well as access to other core-external devices, but typically those are implemented based on the former two mechanisms.

In systems with a mix of complex performance cores and simple reliability cores, UCI allows to shield the reliable core from attacks by the complex core. However, the isolation awarded by UCI also helps systems with homogeneous cores. Even if the same vulnerability is present in all cores, it must be triggered in order to manifest as an isolation failure. In a cloud scenario, customer A may know that their

software does not trigger the vulnerability and A can therefore trust their cores. However, customer A should not need to trust software from customer B to not exploit customer B's cores. To support this trust, UCI must enforce that cores of customer B cannot influence cores from customer A, no matter what software runs on them. In short: even if all cores have the same bug, customer A can still use them correctly but does not rely on B to do the same.

2.3. Trusted computing base

In the software world, the trusted computing base (TCB) describes the set of components that software must rely upon to ensure its correct operation. With regards to inter-component isolation, the TCB encompasses the operating-system kernel. Because UCI encompasses hardware components, we apply the term TCB to include both hardware and software. If two software components run side-by-side, the correctness of their isolation relies on a subset of the underlying hardware and software components. This reliance subset constitutes the TCB.

Isolation *enforcement* is typically implemented in hardware, because monitoring and filtering memory accesses and signaling messages promptly is critical for performance. This hardware is part of the TCB. However, it must not be overlooked that this enforcement component is programmed from somewhere. This *management* part needs to be equally trusted as the enforcement, because it has the power to program wrong enforcement policies or disable them altogether. Management is thus also part of the TCB.

As we will see in the UCI candidates discussion, management is typically implemented in software as part of the operating-system kernel. In this case, the entire core on which the operating system runs is also part of the TCB, because vulnerabilities in that core may be exploited to trick the kernel into mis-programming the enforcement.

2.4. Attacker model

The UCI attacker model starts by labeling cores as trusted and untrusted: The *target* software whose operation we want to protect runs on cores we consider trusted. We also trust the entire TCB to operate correctly and implement isolation according to UCI requirements. The software running on untrusted cores is a potential *attacker* or can be commanded by an attacker.

Since we assume cores to be arbitrarily broken, the strongest possible attacker can fully exercise all interfaces of the core to the rest of the platform. Thus we cannot rely on any isolation features that are provided by the core itself (e.g., privilege levels). Even with arbitrarily broken cores, UCI must enforce isolation so that the attacker can only influence its own core and utilize consensually established communication channels. Specifically, reads and writes to target-owned memory outside of explicitly established shared-memory areas must be prevented. Additionally, unwanted signaling messages from the attacker must not reach the target. In the case that no communication channels are configured between target and attacker, any influence from the attacker to the target must be blocked.

We do however define the following attacks as out-of-scope for this paper: (1) We do not handle physical attacks on the hardware. Orthogonal to UCI, attacks on memory and exposed system buses can be mitigated by memory encryption as provided for example by AMD SEV [35]. (2) We do not handle software-controlled attacks on physical properties of the hardware, such as undervolting [36,37] or DRAM row hammering [38]. UCI can help to reduce the impact of these attacks but must be combined with additional attack-specific countermeasures. (3) We also do not handle pure software vulnerabilities or software side channels. If some attacker-to-target communication is allowed and the target software contains a bug, the attacker can exploit it without UCI preventing this. UCI can isolate cores or allow them to interact, but any allowed interaction opens the target to software-level attacks, including timing side channels such as NetSpectre [39].

Hardening against software vulnerabilities and ensuring constant-time request processing is orthogonal to UCI.

In this paper, we focus on attacks based on vulnerabilities in the core itself. This includes cache-based side-channel attacks such as Spectre [1], Meltdown [2], and Fallout [7] that can be used to leak data from victims, micro-architectural bugs such as $\text{\AE}P\text{IC}$ [3] that also allow data leaks, and also vulnerabilities such as GhostWrite [29] that provide attackers write access to victim data. We discuss the attacks that UCI can prevent and its limitations in more detail in Section 5.1.

3. Candidates using existing building blocks

In this section, we take existing systems or existing components and analyze whether they are suitable to completely isolate a single core from other cores. We will start with typical commodity systems found on current mobile and desktop devices to illustrate the problem, continue with network-connected machines to maximize the isolation between applications, and finally converge to single machine solutions based on IOMMUs, SR-IOV NICs, and IPIs. In the following, we explain these approaches in detail, all based on Fig. 1, and derive requirements and lessons learned that we will later use for a clean-slate redesign.

3.1. Shared kernel with MMUs

We start with a typical multicore processor, depicted on the left in Fig. 1, with a single operating system (OS) running as a shared kernel on all cores. This setup is found on many current embedded, desktop, and server platforms. All cores are connected to a shared memory and the OS kernel uses address spaces provided by the MMU¹ to both isolate itself from user applications and to isolate user applications from each other. This scenario has two applications running on the OS: a target application that needs to execute securely in terms of confidentiality and integrity, and an attacker application that tries to compromise the target. For example, the target could be a control loop on an IoT device that interacts with the physical world or a customer in a datacenter that processes security-critical data. In both cases, the attacker should not be able to manipulate the execution of the target or extract information from the target. For that reason, the OS isolates these applications from each other using address spaces as provided by the MMU. This isolation is based on the correct functioning of all the components shown with a bold frame in Fig. 1. These components form the isolation TCB, which includes isolation enforcement (MMU, shown in green) and isolation management (OS, shown in blue).

As stated in Section 2, our goal is to isolate software components from each other but also allow communication channels between them. To keep the scenario simple we do not introduce a third application, but assume that the attacker application has a communication channel to the target. As depicted in the figure, we call the first approach IPIs+MMU: it uses shared memory (SHM) to exchange data and inter-processor interrupts (IPIs) for cross-core signaling. We start with shared hardware resources, followed by the implications of arbitrarily broken cores.

3.1.1. Shared hardware resources

Typical multicore processors contain large micro-architectural state in caches, translation look-aside buffers (TLBs), and branch target buffers (BTBs). This micro-architectural state is often shared between cores or at least between multiple hardware threads within a core. If this state is shared, attackers can leak data from other processes [1, 4], the OS kernel [4,7], or SGX enclaves [4,5]. We therefore derive that micro-architectural state must not be shared between target and attacker core. Specifically, target and attacker must run on different cores, not only different hardware threads.

Requirement: Micro-architectural state must not be shared with untrusted cores.

¹ We use MMUs as an example isolation mechanism for simplicity. Our claims hold for other core-based isolation mechanisms such as MPUs as well.

Fig. 1. Comparison of approaches with existing building blocks to remove the core of a potential attacker from the TCB of the target. Red indicates vulnerable components, green indicates isolation enforcement, and blue indicates isolation management. Components with bold frames are part of the target's TCB and machine boundaries are indicated with dashed lines. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

3.1.2. Isolation enforcement with vulnerable cores

Without shared micro-architectural state one could think that everything is fine and the target can execute without any disturbance by the attacker. However, if the core has an arbitrary vulnerability (indicated by the red color in Fig. 1), as we assume for UCI, these measures are not sufficient. The reason is that cores have unrestricted access to physical memory and all other resources in the system. Thus, like an exploitable bug in the OS kernel, an exploitable bug in the core also allows the attacker to take over the system. For example, a bug in the store architecture that allows to bypass the MMU checks would allow an attacker to overwrite kernel memory and thereby take control of the kernel. This problem has two underlying reasons. While the MMU does enforce isolation between different software components, it is integrated with the potentially vulnerable core and therefore cannot be used to isolate cores from each other. In other words, the target cannot trust the attacker's core to restrict itself.

Requirement: Isolation enforcement must be separated from the vulnerable core.

Note that separating the MMU from the core in order to place trust into the MMU, but not into the rest of the core, is challenging. The idea would be to configure the MMUs of the cores externally and with that restrict access to physical memory. However, the fundamental issue is that the MMU does not simply receive virtual addresses from the core and then sends physical addresses to the memory. Instead, the MMU is inherently entangled with the rest of the core and the resulting physical addresses are fed back to many components deep inside the core such as caches, TLBs, line fill buffers, and store buffers. Since these core components can erroneously change the physical addresses, the MMU protection can be subverted. Thus, separately trusting the MMU but not the core is not justified.

3.1.3. Isolation management with vulnerable cores

After isolation enforcement, we now discuss the component managing the isolation: the OS. With MMUs, the OS creates address spaces and manipulates page-table entries to provide and restrict access to physical memory. For that reason, an exploitable bug in the OS allows the attacker to compromise isolation between applications. Microkernels therefore reduce the attack surface of the OS by splitting it into multiple isolated but communicating components that run on top of a small kernel. However, traditional monolithic kernels and microkernel-based systems run a shared kernel on all cores, including the attacker core we do not want to trust. Therefore, sharing the same kernel between the core of the attacker and the target allows the attacker to compromise the target by exploiting a bug in the attacker's core.

Requirement: Kernels must not be shared between cores.

Qian Ge et al. have also shown based on seL4 that microkernels can go further and prevent timing channels between different trust domains with a separate clone of the microkernel for each trust domain [40]. Similarly, per-core kernel instances in multikernels [41] make it easier to fully isolate cores from each other, because they do not need to operate on the same memory, but the problem remains the same: we rely on the correctness of all cores, because all cores have unrestricted access to all resources in the system.

Requirement: Isolation management must not run on potentially vulnerable cores.

Note that this requirement is distinct from the previous one, because a separate entity for isolation management does not imply per-core kernel instances and vice versa. Supporting vulnerable cores requires a separate isolation management to reliably control the access permissions of each core and per-core kernel instances to ensure that exploiting a bug in one core does not impact other cores.

3.1.4. Secure signaling with vulnerable cores

As stated, the IPIs+MMU approach uses shared memory for data transfers and inter-processor interrupts (IPIs) for signaling. Current multicore platforms already provide interrupt controllers (shown as "IRQ Ctrl". in the figure) to send IPIs to other cores. Such signaling allows to build synchronization primitives without relying on polling, which is crucial for energy-efficient solutions. However, current platforms do not allow to externally restrict who can send IPIs to which cores, but instead rely on the cores and the privileged software layers to use the mechanism responsibly. An attacker could take advantage of this and, for example, send interrupt storms to arbitrary other cores.

Requirement: Signaling mechanisms must be restricted externally, instead of relying on responsible use by cores.

3.2. Network-connected machines

Considering the requirements we learned so far, isolating cores from each other on the same machine seems challenging. Therefore, we want to continue at the other end of the spectrum by isolating target and attacker in the strongest conceivable way: put them on different, physically separated machines. This network approach is depicted in the second column of Fig. 1. Both machines have their own memory and their own operating system and thus, do not share any resources.

Communication between the machines is possible over network via the network interface card (NIC) in each machine. Remote direct memory access (RDMA) functionality of modern NICs can be used to transfer data between machines. Messages can be used for signaling.

With network-connected machines, the attacker is fully isolated from the target via an air gap (indicated by the green area between the two machines). The target's TCB does not contain any component of the attacker's machine, because no resources are shared and the attacker has no way to manipulate or disturb the target. The target only needs to trust its own underlying OS and core. Additionally, it may have to trust the NIC regarding confidentiality and integrity, unless all network traffic is cryptographically secured.

3.2.1. Shared state in distributed systems

While the network approach fulfills the UCI goals regarding isolation, challenges remain regarding communication and collaboration between the machines. Multiple machines form a distributed system, requiring complex consensus protocols unless some trust can be placed in the other machines. Furthermore, shared memory is no longer available, so that work on shared state is more involved. Distributed shared memory [42] can allow the same programming model as on a single machine but cannot achieve the same performance.

Lesson learned: Lack of shared memory complicates the implementation of shared state.

3.2.2. Identification in distributed systems

As indicated by the figure, the network approach lacks isolation management. Without further measures, the target communicating with service A on another machine, does not know whether it actually communicates with service A or with someone else pretending to be service A (man-in-the-middle attack). This problem can be solved with cryptographic protocols (e.g., transport layer security) based on pre-shared keys. This solution introduces stable identifiers for communication endpoints, but does not prevent unwanted communication and therefore remains open for denial-of-service attacks.

Requirement: Trustworthy communication requires unforgeable identifiers and traffic control.

Datacenters achieve trustworthy communication within the network fabric. Machines are networked via programmable switches, which control and label communication independent of the potentially untrustworthy participating machines. Isolation management is provided by the management plane of the datacenter. An evolution of programmable switches is the recent trend of smart NICs as part of the datacenter fabric. AWS Nitro [43] and Azure AccelNet [44] are two examples. The architecture of those NICs is such that they contain a processor with its own memory on board, forming an execution environment that is fully isolated from the host machine. Therefore, those NICs act as a trustworthy bridgehead inside every machine and run portions of the datacenter management code. This distribution allows to implement isolation management within the NIC itself, close to the machine being managed, but still isolated from it. The management component can maintain stable identification of communication partners and permission management of communication channels throughout the datacenter. Both the Smart NIC solution and programmable switches fulfill the goals of UCI, albeit in a very heavyweight fashion.

3.3. SR-IOV NICs and IOMMUs

Considering the desired isolation properties from the network approach, we now try to pull the relevant components back into a single

machine in order to avoid the problems that come with distributed systems. The approach is called SR-IOV+IOMMU, depicted in the third column of Fig. 1, and works as follows: Each application is provided with its own OS to protect it against attacks on other OSes. For simplicity, we ignore the virtualization layer used in datacenters and run both OSes on bare metal. Communication between applications is done via NIC based on RDMA and messages as in the network approach. Since each OS needs to be able to use the NIC independently, we use a NIC with support for single-root I/O virtualization (SR-IOV), which allows to create multiple virtual NICs (vNIC) from a single physical NIC. Thus, each application has its own vNIC assigned.

With these building blocks in place, applications can communicate with each other. However, we also want to control who can communicate with whom. For that reason and inspired by programmable switches, we introduce a separate core that runs an isolation manager, which selectively allows communication. This can be done by assigning two applications to the same VLAN.

This setup successfully isolates applications from each other with selectively allowed communication and is also used in today's datacenters, but only with the assumption that all cores work correctly. At first, both OSes access their vNIC via its associated memory-mapped I/O (MMIO) area in the physical address space. Without the ability to control which core can access which part of the physical address space, all cores are free to use all vNICs. Second, this approach still has the problem illustrated with the MMU-based isolation: all cores have unrestricted access to physical memory and can thereby compromise each other's OSes, for example. To solve this problem we propose to add a kind-of IOMMU externally to each core, which restricts the memory accesses of the core, similarly as done today for I/O devices. The isolation manager is responsible for configuring the IOMMUs. IOMMUs receive physical addresses from the core and ensure that access is granted before sending the request to memory. This usage of IOMMUs to restrict cores instead of peripherals is unconventional but not without precedent. Some embedded platforms targeting safety-critical applications use IOMMUs to isolate the safety-critical core from auxiliary cores.

Note that SR-IOV also relies on IOMMUs at the NIC to restrict the memory access of individual vNICs in order to prevent that users of the vNIC can leverage the vNIC to access physical memory they are not supposed to access. These are still necessary, but we do not show them for simplicity here.

In summary, cores only have access to the physical address space as granted by the isolation manager and can selectively communicate via SR-IOV NIC, also only as granted by the isolation manager. The enforcement of these restrictions is handled by the IOMMU regarding memory accesses and by the SR-IOV NIC regarding VLAN access. The TCB of the target therefore does not contain the core and OS of the attacker. However, while fulfilling UCI requirements, using a NIC for on-device communication with SR-IOV support to let cores work independently and VLANs to isolate communication channels is arguably rather heavyweight. In our evaluation, we observe about an order of magnitude difference in latency.

Lesson learned: Isolation of cores is possible with slight adjustments of existing building blocks but heavyweight.

4. Clean-slate redesign

After the discussion of existing approaches we now want to take the requirements and lessons learned and construct a clean-slate redesign. We start by collecting the necessary features from existing SR-IOV NICs, IOMMUs, and interrupt controllers and merge them into a new hardware component. Based on this component, we elaborate on how this component can be used to secure a commodity platform. Finally, we present the research prototype M³, which closely matches our envisaged architecture, demonstrating its feasibility.

4.1. The trusted communication unit

Based on the insights from the previous section, we now want to combine the required functionalities of existing components into a new hardware component that is specifically designed to isolate cores and to selectively allow communication. This component is called *Trusted Communication Unit* (TCU) and is placed between every core and the memory subsystem, like the interrupt controller and IOMMU in Fig. 1 before. The TCU is configured externally by the isolation manager. For example, the isolation manager could run on a simple and more trustworthy core that is integrated next to the complex and therefore potentially vulnerable cores. Like the IOMMU, the TCU enforces the restrictions on memory accesses that are defined by the isolation manager. We additionally propose to equip the TCU with message-passing functionality to specifically support signaling and message-based data exchange between cores. Message arrival can trigger interrupts to notify the core. Like with memory access, message-passing channels are configured by the isolation manager and the TCU enforces the communication restrictions. Finally, messages contain an identifier, added by the TCU and therefore unforgeable for the sender, which enables receivers to reliably distinguish between senders.

4.2. Securing a commodity platform

In the next step, we want to discuss how a commodity platform can be secured based on the TCU. We start with a typical multi-core system with shared caches, a per-core interrupt controller, a shared DRAM, and I/O devices. At first, we pull cores apart by turning shared hardware resources into per-core resources and integrate a TCU next to every core. Like with tiled architectures [45], every core is integrated in its own tile and tiles are connected to a network-on-chip (NoC) for communication. The access to the NoC is secured by the TCU, because all NoC accesses from the core go through the TCU. Secure cross-core signaling is performed via TCU instead of the per-core interrupt controller. This organization provides memory and interrupt isolation between cores and can selectively allow cross-core communication through the TCU's message passing functionality.

Despite this strict separation of cores, shared hardware resources can be supported. For example, all cores can get access to a shared DRAM by integrating the memory controller into a dedicated tile. Accessing the DRAM from a core requires NoC communication and is therefore secured by the TCU. The TCU can restrict these accesses to securely share the DRAM. For example, TCUs can be configured to partition the DRAM into per-core regions with one additional shared region for data exchange. Similarly, a shared L3 cache can be integrated into dedicated tiles in addition to per-core L1 and L2 caches. In fact, contemporary processors already employ sliced L3 caches with an interconnect linking the slices to the cores. Finally, I/O devices can be connected by integrating controllers like a PCIe roots as individual tiles and therefore receive their own TCU as well. This TCU would replace traditional IOMMUs by restricting memory accesses and signals to device-driver cores.

We believe that such organization is feasible despite open questions such as its performance implications or the required changes to current OSes. However, instead of discussing these questions on the reorganized commodity platform, we now turn to a research prototype that closely resembles this organization in order to demonstrate the feasibility.

4.3. M^3 as a closely matching research system

M^3 [19] proposes a new system architecture based on a hardware/software co-design and fulfills all UCI requirements. Like with the reorganized commodity platform, M^3 builds upon a tiled architecture and integrates a new hardware component into every tile as shown in Fig. 2. This hardware component is called data transfer unit (DTU), but fulfills the same role as the proposed TCU so that we also call it TCU henceforth.

Fig. 2. System architecture of M^3 : one TCU per tile enforces isolation between tiles and selectively allows communication as defined by the M^3 kernel (isolation manager). TileMux multiplexes its tile among the applications on this tile.

4.3.1. Isolation enforcement

The TCU supports both memory access and message passing to form *communication channels* (thick black lines in the figure) between tiles. Communication channels are represented as *endpoints* in the TCU (orange dots). At runtime, each endpoint can be configured to different endpoint types: A *receive endpoint* allows to receive messages, a *send endpoint* allows to send messages to a specific receive endpoint, and a *memory endpoint* allows to issue DMA requests to tile-external memory. This concept also extends to heterogeneous systems with accelerators [20], but we focus on general-purpose cores in this work.

Message passing is performed between a pair of send and receive endpoints and can be used for cross-tile signaling with optional payload. Both endpoints store properties about the communication channel, which are checked by the TCU. For example, send endpoints store the tile and receive endpoint of the associated recipient and receive endpoints store the allowed message size. Messages consist of a header and a payload. The header is defined by the TCU, whereas the payload is defined by software. Among others, the header contains a *label* that is unforgeable by the sender and thus allows the recipient to reliably identify senders. Furthermore, a credit system is used for flow control and to prevent denial-of-service attacks. Each receiver hands out credits to its senders, stored in each of the send endpoints. Sending a message requires at least one credit in the send endpoint and the TCU reduces the number of credits by one. Each received message allows the receiver to reply once to that message and thereby give the credit back to the sender (with optional payload).

Memory access is based on memory endpoints, which in contrast to send and receive endpoints do not come in pairs. Instead, each memory endpoint refers to a memory region without an endpoint on the memory side. Each memory endpoint stores the base address, size, and access permissions of the region in memory. In contrast to send and receive endpoints, which are always used explicitly by the software, memory endpoints can be used explicitly to issue DMA requests and are used implicitly during memory accesses. More specifically, the tile's last-level cache routes memory requests upon cache misses through the TCU, which validates them based on memory endpoints.

4.3.2. Isolation management

On the software side, M^3 runs its kernel (blue) on a dedicated *kernel tile*, and applications and OS services on the remaining *user tiles*. The kernel tile therefore represents the role of the isolation manager in the system that decides resource access permissions and permitted communication channels for the user tiles. Applications and OS services on user tiles are represented as *activities*, comparable to processes. An activity on a general-purpose tile executes code, whereas an activity on an accelerator tile uses the accelerator's logic. The M^3 kernel manages

the permissions of each activity using *capabilities*, similar to other microkernels [31,33,46]. A capability is a pair of a reference to a resource and permissions for this resource. Each activity starts with an empty set of capabilities, but capabilities can be created and exchanged between activities via the M^3 kernel. For example, one activity can create a memory capability and thereby allocate memory and then pass this capability to another activity to establish shared memory. Message-passing channels are created analogously.

The M^3 kernel is therefore responsible for managing the capabilities of all activities in the system and to establish communication channels between user tiles. Establishing communication channels requires the ability to change endpoints in other TCUs. For that reason, TCUs can be privileged and unprivileged. All TCUs start privileged at boot and TCUs in user tiles are then downgraded to unprivileged by the M^3 kernel. Only privileged TCUs can freely change their own endpoints, which allows them, for example, to create a memory endpoint that refers to the MMIO region of another tile's TCU and thereby change its endpoints. Applications running on user tiles therefore cannot change their own endpoints and are thus relying on the M^3 kernel to get access to tile-external resources. However, applications can use existing endpoints directly via the TCU's MMIO region, which is crucial for good performance.

4.3.3. Tile multiplexing

By default, applications are placed on different tiles, but as shown by M^3v [21], tiles with general-purpose cores can also be shared efficiently and securely among multiple applications. For that reason, every core in user tiles runs a multiplexer called *TileMux* (yellow in Fig. 2), which is responsible for isolating and scheduling the applications on its own tile, similar to a traditional kernel. However, in contrast to a kernel, each *TileMux* instance has no permissions beyond its own tile. Instead, only the M^3 kernel can make system-wide decisions, hence its name. The M^3 kernel runs on a separate tile and can use a simpler and therefore more trustworthy core. Despite the split of responsibilities and independent *TileMux* instances, the kernel and *TileMux* instances work together to provide applications with a shared-system experience: Applications on all tiles use the same abstractions, have access to shared system services, and can collaborate even when running on different *TileMux* instances.

4.3.4. Policy enforcement

After describing the basic responsibilities of the TCU, the M^3 kernel, and *TileMux*, we now explain how they work together to define and enforce security policies. For example, someone needs to decide who can communicate with whom or who can access which memory regions and someone needs to define limits on message sizes or NoC bandwidth. To keep the trusted computing base as small, M^3 does not use a potentially complex policy engine in the TCU. Instead, M^3 builds upon a layered approach to keep the lower layers simple and therefore trustworthy. The first layer is responsible for managing and distributing resources to services and applications in a rather coarse-grained fashion. In the second layer, these resources are translated into capabilities, so there can be a fine-grained exchange of resources between services and applications. The third layer is responsible for enforcing the restrictions that have been set for individual applications. For performance reasons, this enforcement is performed locally at the component responsible for the resource.

Resource management and distribution In more detail, the first layer uses XML-based *configuration files* to describe the distribution of resources and *resource managers* that read this configuration file and manage the resources accordingly. The overall idea is to use one configuration file per use case of the system (each boot expects exactly one configuration file), which describes the services and applications that should be started including their accessible resources and limits.

There is always at least one resource manager, but nesting of resource managers to create subsystems is supported. Each resource

manager receives the subset of the configuration file it is responsible for and starts the therein requested services and applications. Each child additionally receives a communication channel to its resource manager. Children use this channel to request access to resources, which the resource manager checks against the configuration file. In case access can be granted, it creates a capability for the resource and passes it to the child.

Fine-granular exchange via capabilities These capabilities are handled by the second layer. That is, capabilities are managed in software by the M^3 kernel, which offers system calls to create, exchange, and revoke capabilities. After receiving an initial capability from the resource manager, applications can pass on the capability to other applications, provided that communication channels to the applications exist.

Furthermore, the M^3 kernel supports *derivation* of capabilities. Derivation creates a new capability from an existing one with a specified quota or permission subset. For example, the tile capability holds multiple quotas for tile-local resources such as CPU time and NoC bandwidth. Starting an activity on a tile requires a tile capability and uses the attached quotas for this activity. For that reason, if activity A has a tile capability with 1s CPU time and 4 GB/s NoC bandwidth, activity A can derive from this tile capability and thereby move 0.5s of CPU time and 3 GB/s of NoC bandwidth to a new tile capability. Afterwards, a new activity B can be started with this derived tile capability, which will be constrained to these resource limits. The tile capability of activity A has been reduced by the derive to 0.5s CPU time and 1 GB/s NoC bandwidth.

Enforcement of restrictions The third layer is responsible for enforcing restrictions on resource accesses. These restrictions are based on quotas and are enforced locally by the component that embodies the resource. Local enforcement is important to achieve good performance, because it avoids the involvement of other components during access time. For that reason, resource limits are enforced by different components, depending on the resource. For example, *TileMux* is responsible for enforcing limits on CPU time, whereas the TCU enforces limits on message sizes, memory permissions (read/write), and NoC bandwidth.

In summary, this layered approach provides a convenient and flexible XML-based way to express the distribution of resources and communication permissions, but keeps the lowest layers and in particular the TCU simple, because these are only enforcing the limits as chosen by the upper layers. For example, determining whether a particular application can use a specific service and what message sizes are permitted involves XML parsing and capability exchanges, but the TCU only needs to check whether a specific endpoint is present and if the message size is within the limit.

4.3.5. Trusted computing base

Now that the basic system architecture of M^3 is known, we discuss its trusted computing base with focus on the goals of UCI. Like existing microkernel-based systems, M^3 has a system-wide TCB that all components have to trust and application-specific TCBs that build upon the system-wide TCB.

The system-wide TCB consists of all TCUs, the NoC between TCUs, and the M^3 kernel including the core it is running on. Additionally, the shared DRAM is considered trusted, although this can be relaxed via memory encryption. All TCUs need to be trusted regarding confidentiality, integrity, and availability, because they see all communication and decide whether a specific communication or memory access is allowed. For the same reason, the NoC needs to be trusted regarding the same properties. The M^3 kernel can freely configure all communication channels in all TCUs and therefore has also full control over the entire platform.

In contrast to traditional architectures, all cores in user tiles are not part of the TCB and can be arbitrarily broken. That means, even if one core has a bug, applications on other cores are not affected by this bug. For that reason, the TCU is not part of the core, but sits next to the

Fig. 3. Hardware implementation of the TCU. Dashed blocks and arrows indicate optional components.

Fig. 4. Detailed depiction of the TCU's register file.

core only reachable from the core over a well defined interface. Due to the simplicity of the TCU in contrast to modern cores, we believe that trust into the TCU is justified. The simplicity also makes it feasible to formally verify the TCU, which is already work in progress.

4.3.6. Design challenges

After describing the basic system architecture of M³ and how it fulfills the requirements of UCI, we want to highlight a few of the design challenges.

Hardware/software split for communication channels Our goal was to keep the TCU as small and simple as possible, but still achieve the desired flexibility for general-purpose applications. For example, applications should be able to establish shared memory. It may seem natural to equip the TCU with the ability to pass an existing memory endpoint to another TCU to establish shared memory. However, this would have increased the TCUs complexity dramatically. Not only does such functionality require message protocols between TCUs to exchange endpoints, and the ability to search for free endpoints on the receiver side. Most importantly, applications need to be able to remove the access to the shared memory if desired. This in turn requires the TCU to remember such endpoint exchanges to be able to remove all endpoints later on. We therefore opted instead for handling all this complexity on the software side: the M³ kernel uses capabilities and supports their exchange and revocation. The TCU therefore only supports the configuration and invalidation of endpoints, whereas all management, decisions, and protocols are handled in software.

Efficient usage of the TCU Despite its simplicity, we carefully designed the TCU to make TCU-based communication efficient. Most importantly, applications can directly access the TCU via MMIO, allowing to issue a DMA request within a couple of cycles. This requires additional

measures in the TCU to make this secure. For example, the application can only specify the payload of messages, but not the message header. The header is constructed by the TCU, so that the receiver can always rely on the header being correct (e.g., the label of the sender). Furthermore, we introduced a credit system to prevent that malicious applications can DoS attack other components by flooding them with messages. Similarly, the TCU provides a NoC-bandwidth regulation that allows the kernel to limit the available NoC bandwidth on a per-application basis [22]. These measures would not have been necessary if all TCU accesses needed to be done by a privileged and trustworthy component such as the kernel or TileMux. As the additional complexity in the TCU is rather small, we decided for the more efficient solution in this case.

Responsibilities of the M³ kernel and TileMux In contrast to other OSes, M³ employs two components that have similarities with traditional kernels. TileMux uses different CPU modes and paging to shield itself from the applications on its own tile just like traditional kernels. However, TileMux does not provide access to any resources, but implements only a scheduler and low-level memory management. Instead, access to resources is provided by the M³ kernel via capabilities. Like traditional kernels, the M³ kernel has complete control over the entire system (hence the name kernel), but unlike other kernels, it runs alone on a separate tile. There are multiple reasons for this split of responsibilities: (1) supporting potentially buggy cores requires that TileMux has no permissions beyond its own tile. It therefore cannot have access to all applications or all resources in the system. (2) The M³ kernel cannot perform all context switches on all tiles due to efficiency and scalability reasons (see M³v [21] for details). (3) Some paging operations can only be done locally (e.g., setting the page-table base register) and therefore also need to be handled by TileMux.

4.3.7. Hardware implementation

Overview The hardware platform is implemented in Verilog and put on a Xilinx Virtex UltraScale+ FPGA (VCU118 board). The current prototype contains eight processing tiles with a single RISC-V core each and two memory tiles with interfaces to external DDR4 DRAM. All tiles are connected via a 2 × 2 star-mesh network-on-chip (NoC) and each tile contains a TCU, which is depicted in Fig. 3. The TCU is connected to the cache-coherent system bus of the RISC-V core to perform message passing and memory accesses. For example, the TCU loads a message from memory before sending it over the NoC. The TCU has additionally interfaces to support MMIO accesses by the core, and to access the NoC. Last-level cache misses are handled by the TCU's physical memory protection (PMP) to ensure that the accesses are covered by a valid memory endpoint. Furthermore, the TCU has a register file containing the endpoints, unprivileged registers to execute unprivileged commands with the existing endpoints, and privileged registers for TileMux to execute privileged commands (e.g., switch between applications). Both types of commands are implemented by the control unit.

Register interface Fig. 4 zooms into the sketched register file in Fig. 3. The unprivileged registers are accessible to regular applications (activities), whereas the privileged registers are only available to TileMux, the privileged software on each tile. Furthermore, the endpoint registers are only writable for the kernel. Endpoints are 192-bit registers, whereas unprivileged and privileged registers are 64-bit.

Endpoint registers represent communication channels and the TCU contains several of them (128 in the current implementation). All endpoints have a type (T=XYZ) and hold the id of the owning activity, but the rest of the bits are defined on a per-type basis. Endpoints can be changed to different types at runtime and will be interpreted by the TCU accordingly. The kernel is the only component in the system that can write to endpoint registers and thereby define communication channels.

Unprivileged registers are provided to let activities work with endpoints in a controlled manner. The COMMAND register describes a

Table 1

Systematic study of possible attack vectors by walking through the components (right) and showing which attacks can be prevented or mitigated by the UCI model (left).

Attack	Examples	Covered
① Attacks on physical properties	Plundervolt [36], RowHammer [38], cold boot [47]	–
② Bugs in TCB (IsoMng, TCUs, etc.)	–	–
③ DoS attacks over NoC/DRAM	NoC-based [48], DRAM-based [49]	✓
④ Side-channel attacks via NoC/DRAM	ConNOC [50], DramaQueen [51]	–
⑤ Transient execution vuln. in user core	Spectre [1], Fallout [7], RIDL [6]	✓
⑥ Arbitrary bug in user core	GhostWrite [29], Meltdown [2]	✓
⑦ Bugs in OS	Linux CVE-2024-42314 [52]	✓
⑧ Bugs in user software	Google Chrome CVE-2024-4761 [53]	✓
⑨ Software timing bugs	NetSpectre [39]	–

command and triggers its execution, whereas the other registers are used for additional arguments. For example, an activity can instruct the TCU to send a message that it prepared in memory (described by DATA_ADDR and DATA_SIZE) over a specific endpoint. The TCU then verifies whether this endpoint is a send endpoint (T=SND), belongs to the running activity (ACT == CUR_ACTIVITY), the message size is within the limit, and credits are available. If all is fulfilled, the TCU sends the message over the NoC to the recipient. Otherwise, the command fails and the activity can inspect the error code. As all commands finish in short amounts of time, the current implementation indicates their completion via the COMMAND register, which is typically polled by the activity.

Next to send endpoints, memory endpoints (T=MEM) allow to issue DMA requests to a specific memory region (defined by TILE, ADDRESS, and SIZE) with the commands READ and WRITE. Finally, a receive endpoint maintains a ring buffer that is split up into same-sized slots and therefore holds the slot count (BUF-SZ) and slot size (MSG-SZ). Additionally, the TCU uses bit masks to keep track of which slots are occupied (OCC.) and not yet read by software (UNREAD). Receive endpoints support the commands FETCH, which yields the next unread message, ACK to finish the handling of a message, and REPLY to send a reply to a specific message.

The privileged registers are used by TileMux to manage multiple activities on the same tile. For example, it is responsible to change CUR_ACTIVITY when it switches between activities. This is performed via privileged commands, which work analogously to unprivileged commands, but use the registers PRIV_COMMAND and PRIV_COMMAND_ARG.

4.3.8. Software implementation

All important software components of M³ are implemented in Rust due to the memory-safety guarantees the language provides. However, C and C++ APIs are provided as well and legacy applications are supported via a C-Library-based POSIX emulation layer. The M³ kernel consists of 11.5k SLOC (Rust; 900 unsafe). TileMux adds another 1.7k SLOC (Rust; 50 unsafe). In comparison, the NOVA microkernel [33] consists of about 9k SLOC (C++).

4.3.9. Limitations

Although the M³ system architecture fulfills the UCI requirements, it still has a few limitations and open research questions. At first, the tiles are not cache coherent, but interact exclusively via message passing and shared memory accessed by TCU-based DMA requests. The lack of cache coherence makes it hard to run multiple threads within the same address space on multiple tiles, which is therefore currently not supported by M³. Similarly, renting a configurable subset of tiles to a single cloud customer suffers from this limitations. We believe cross-tile cache coherence can be supported while still providing strong isolation between tiles. For example, the TCU could validate cache-coherence traffic to ensure that both participating cores have access to the memory area in question. However, further research is required to evaluate the implications of this idea.

Second, endpoints are integrated into TCUs and thus each TCU offers only a certain number. The hard limit on endpoints restricts

the number of communication channels per applications and also the number of applications per tile, because all applications on a tile share its endpoints. How more endpoints can be supported securely and efficiently is an open research question.

5. Qualitative analysis and comparison

After the clean-slate redesign we now continue with a qualitative analysis of the UCI model. We start with a security analysis that evaluates what kind of attacks can be prevented and which attacks require other means. Afterwards, we compare existing approaches regarding the fulfillment of the UCI requirements.

5.1. Security analysis

We study the effectiveness of the UCI model by systematically walking through all participating components and their associated attack vectors and analyzing whether the UCI model can either prevent or mitigate these attacks. The attacks including real-world examples and their coverage by the UCI model are shown in Table 1 with the locations of the individual attacks on the right (green components are part of the TCB, red ones are not).

The first class of attacks leverages physical properties of the hardware (①) such as voltages [36] or undesirable side effects between DRAM cells [38]. These attacks cannot be prevented by UCI and thus need additional countermeasures. The UCI model can also not prevent attacks that exploit vulnerabilities in UCI's TCB (②) as it assumes that these components work correctly. Due to the simplicity of the TCU and the isolation manager, formal verification could be used to increase the trust in these components. Denial-of-service (DoS) attacks over a shared NoC or DRAM (③) can be prevented by a credit system as demonstrated by M³. However, timing attacks based on these shared resources (④) are still left for future work.

In contrast to existing point mitigations such as KPTI [16], UCI defends against arbitrary bugs in user cores (⑤, ⑥) if the victim runs on a different tile than the attacker. In other words, although the bugs itself might still exist in user cores, UCI prevents that they can be used to attack other tiles. Similarly, the OS that runs on a user tile has no permissions beyond its own tile, limiting the impact of bugs (⑦) to the same tile. Bugs in user software (⑧) are also contained within the same tile and traditional means such as address spaces and different CPU modes can be used to shield them from other software on the same tile (as shown by TileMux).

Software-only timing issues (⑨) like operations requiring varying periods of time cannot be prevented by UCI though, and thus need additional protection.

5.2. Comparison and related work

We now compare existing approaches regarding the fulfillment of the requirements of the UCI model, whose results are shown in Table 2. The presented solutions are grouped by the degree of modification they require: software-only concepts running on commodity hardware (using IPIs + MMU), additional hardware components, core extensions,

Table 2

Comparison of various approaches regarding the requirements of UCI and other desirable properties. The approaches are split into groups, which are sorted from left to right by the degree of modifications they require.

Requirement	Off-the-shelf HW	Monolith/ μ -kernel	SW-based Isolation	Multikernel	Network	Inter-core Isolation	SR-IOV + IOMMU	NoC-MPU / DPU	Core Extensions	CHERI	Trustzone / Sanctum	SGX / TDX / SEV	Sancus	Alternative Platforms	Apple SEP / AMD PSP	Enzian / OpenPiton	Core Slicing	M ³
No shared micro-architectural state	?	?	?	✓	✓	?	?	-	-	-	-	-	-	✓	?	?	?	✓
No shared kernel	-	-	-	✓	✓	(S)	✓	-	-	-	-	-	-	✓	?	?	✓	✓
Separate isolation enforcement	-	-	-	-	✓	(S)	✓	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	?	?	-	✓
Separate isolation management	-	-	-	-	?	(S)	?	-	-	-	-	-	-	✓	?	?	✓	✓
Unforgeable identifiers	-	-	-	-	?	✓	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	✓	?	?	✓	✓
Secure signaling mechanism	-	-	-	-	?	(S)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	?	-	-	✓
Usability Feature																		
Shared memory	✓	✓	✓	-	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	-	✓	✓	✓
Cache coherence	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	-	✓	✓	✓	-

and finally significant changes to the hardware platform as a whole. Within the table, we denote the lack of a security property with – and its presence with ✓. A question mark indicates that a solution does not conceptually prohibit the implementation of a certain feature, but the concrete work does not provide it. Lastly, (✓) marks features that are only present for the respective approach when using the extensions proposed in this paper.

5.2.1. Off-the-shelf hardware

Most off-the-shelf system architectures fall into this category, providing both shared memory as well as cache coherence. However, regardless of the OS architecture on top, most security requirements for UCI are not met. This holds for both monolithic systems such as Linux as well as for microkernel designs such as Fiasco.OC [32] or seL4 [31]. Software-based isolation [54] requires no MMUs, but relies on the compiler and type-safe languages to disallow unauthorized memory accesses. However, many existing attacks do not require unauthorized memory accesses [1,4,6,9]. Multikernel designs such as Barrelfish [41] and the time-protected flavor of seL4 [40] provide additional security with different kernel instances on each core. In summary, all these approaches are incapable of providing isolation measures that mitigate the impact of faulty cores.

5.2.2. Network

When isolating trust domains by running them on different machines as in datacenter management frameworks [43,44], the domains do neither share microarchitectural state nor a kernel instance. Since the isolation enforcement is done at the NIC or at the switch, it is separated from the potentially flawed compute cores. The availability of the remaining isolation requirements depends on the type of implementation. When using a VLAN-enabled smart switch to separate the trust domains, the isolation management is offloaded to the switch. As the source port of a packet is known to a smart switch, unforgeable identifiers and secure messaging can be provided.

5.2.3. Inter-core isolation

The solutions presented in this category build on top of commodity architectures so both shared memory as well as cache coherence are available. Since both the SR-IOV solution described earlier as well as approaches that restrict the communication over the NoC [55,56] allow for pinning trust domains to different cores, the sharing of microarchitectural state is implementation dependent. While NoC restrictions do not make any assumptions about the kernel type used, the SR-IOV approach relies on a single hypervisor that has the same problems as a shared kernel. With the SR-IOV solution the enforcement of isolation is only separate from the compute cores if additional per-core IOMMU-like components as proposed above are present. The same

holds for the isolation management which is normally done on the compute cores. In contrast, with existing NoC-restriction frameworks isolation enforcement is separate from compute cores by design since it is implemented inside the NoC-MPU / DPU coprocessors. These approaches conceptually also permit to place the isolation management on a dedicated core. Since the NIC adds VLAN tags at the sender side, receivers can use these as unforgeable identifiers. Signaling via network packets between cores can be controlled by VLANs, but the typically available IPI functionality (e.g., LAPIC) needs to be restricted or removed entirely. Inter-core isolation approaches such as NoC-MPU do not cover message passing and hence neither provide identifiers for messages nor impose any restrictions on cross-core signaling.

5.2.4. Core extensions

There exist a variety of approaches for isolating mutually distrusting domains that run on the same core by extending the core itself. These solutions comprise hardware capabilities for memory protection [57] as well as secure enclaves for ARM cores [58], x86-based CPUs [35,59–61], and microcontrollers [62]. While all of these solutions retain the memory sharing and cache coherence properties of their underlying core architecture, they do not yield isolation benefits with respect to UCI since the modifications are made in the untrusted cores themselves.

A different approach is taken by TrustGuard [63], where a complex core is not connected directly to the system bus, but via a Sentry component, which checks the correctness of the computed results. The Sentry is implemented in less than half the logic of an in-order core, but performance is close to that of the complex core.

5.2.5. Alternative platforms

Secure coprocessors such as Apple SEP [17] or AMD PSP [18] can cryptographically prove their identity, thus fulfilling the requirement for unforgeable tokens. Moreover, co-processor and main processor do not share any memory, kernel, or microarchitectural state. However, both SEP as well as PSP are specifically designed for the separation of two trust domains and therefore lack mechanisms for isolation enforcement and signaling restrictions, which are required for a more general design. Research platforms such as Enzian [64] or OpenPiton [65,66] give a system implementor a large degree of freedom for designing both the hardware and software of a platform but do not come with any security properties built in by default.

Zhou et al. [67] proposed to create *core slices* to securely share cloud platforms. Although cores are not shared, this approach relies on a correct implementation of cache partitioning for L2 and L3, potentially leaving shared state. While isolation management is separate, isolation enforcement is still performed by the potentially vulnerable core. Secure signaling is challenging as the origin of IPIs is unknown, so that cores cannot be punished for IPI storms.

As explained before, M^3 [19] uses a tiled architecture with per-tile isolation enforcement and isolation management on a dedicated tile and thereby fulfills all security-related requirements for UCI. However, in its current state, M^3 does not implement cache coherence.

6. Quantitative comparison

We now perform a quantitative comparison of the most important approaches used in Section 3 and M^3 to evaluate the costs and benefits of the UCI. Namely, we use the IPIs+MMU approach as the performance baseline without strong isolation between cores and compare it with the best off-the-shelf candidate with strong isolation (SR-IOV+IOMMU approach) and the M^3 research prototype that fulfills the security requirements of UCI.

6.1. Evaluation platforms

We use M^3 's software and the FPGA-based hardware platform, which are both available as open source [68]. The FPGA platform of M^3 is implemented on the Xilinx Virtex UltraScale+ FPGA (VCU118 board), contains eight processing tiles with a single RISC-V core each and two memory tiles with interfaces to external DDR4 DRAM. All tiles are connected by a NoC using a 2×2 star-mesh topology. The platform uses Rocket cores [69] and BOOM cores [70] as the RISC-V cores. Rocket is a 64-bit RISC-V in-order core with MMU and 16 KiB L1 cache, each for instructions and data, as well as a shared 512 KiB L2 cache. BOOM is the out-of-order variant of Rocket with the same cache configuration. The clock frequencies of the Rocket and BOOM cores are set to 100 MHz and 80 MHz, respectively, to fully meet timing requirements during FPGA synthesis and place-and-route. The M^3 kernel runs on a Rocket core.

We compare M^3 to both the IPIs+MMU approach and the SR-IOV+IOMMU approach without IOMMUs to isolate cores from each other. In other words, we optimistically assume that such IOMMUs do not add any overhead. For both approaches we use an Ampere Altra machine with 80 ARMv8 cores on a single socket. Each core has 64 KiB L1 cache, each for instructions and data, and a 1 MiB L2 cache. The Altra machine has 256 GiB DDR4 DRAM and a Mellanox MT416842 BlueField SmartNIC. We run Linux 5.10 on the Altra machine and configure a fixed frequency of 2.8 GHz for all cores. Due to the different clock frequencies on the FPGA and the Altra machine, we use clock cycles throughout all measurements to make the results more comparable. We also pin all software components with all approaches to different cores in all measurements to prevent scheduling overhead.

6.2. Communication primitives

We start our performance evaluation with micro-benchmarks to study the basic primitives of all three approaches (IPIs+MMU, SR-IOV+IOMMU, and M^3). Since the compute performance is orthogonal to all three approaches, we focus on communication primitives. Namely, we evaluate the performance of remote procedure calls (RPCs), which are used for synchronization and control messages, and memory transfers, which are used to exchange large amounts of data.

The IPIs+MMU approach uses shared memory for both communication primitives. RPCs are implemented by copying the request or response to the shared memory area and using atomic operations to synchronize with the communication partner. Note that we chose to use polling-based synchronization to focus on the performance of the hardware instead of the OS kernel. Memory transfers are implemented with a `memcpy`. The IPIs+MMU approach therefore acts as a performance baseline without isolation between cores.

The SR-IOV+IOMMU approach implements cross-core communication by means of virtual functions created from an RDMA-capable NIC. To increase performance, our implementation makes use of RDMA verbs (`Libibverbs`). RPCs are realized as standard SEND operations

Fig. 5. RPC latency comparison with varying message sizes between IPIs+MMU (atomic instructions and memcpy), M^3 (TCU messages), and SR-IOV+IOMMU (RDMA SEND).

Fig. 6. Memory-transfer latency comparison with varying data sizes between IPIs+MMU (`memcpy`), M^3 -`memcpy` (`memcpy`), M^3 -`tcu` (TCU WRITE), and SR-IOV+IOMMU (RDMA WRITE).

with explicit acknowledgment on the receiver side, while data transfers use RDMA `write`, a one-sided communication primitive that allows for manipulating remote memory.

M^3 uses the TCU to implement RPCs and memory transfers. RPCs send a message via a send endpoint to the receiver, which replies to that message to send the response back to the sender. Memory transfers are implemented by writing to DRAM with a memory endpoint. Like for the other approaches, polling is used to wait for the completion of these TCU operations.

The micro-benchmark evaluates the performance of RPCs and memory transfers depending on the message and data size. On M^3 , the benchmark components are running on BOOM cores. For SR-IOV+IOMMU we use the standard Infiniband tool `ibv_rc_pingpong`. As mentioned, all times are measured in cycles to abstract over the different clock frequencies. Fig. 5 shows the average RPC latency and standard deviation of 1000 runs after 100 warmup runs with message sizes between 1 Byte and 2032 Byte. We used 2032 Byte as the maximum message size, because the TCU does not support larger payloads for messages, in contrast to the other approaches. Note that we do not show the standard deviation for SR-IOV+IOMMU, because `ibv_rc_pingpong` does not report it. As depicted in the figure, both M^3 and IPIs+MMU show comparable results, whereas SR-IOV+IOMMU is more than one order of magnitude slower. We suspect the communication via the off-chip PCIe bus (in contrast to the on-chip communication with M^3 and IPIs+MMU) as the main cause.

Fig. 6 shows the averages and standard deviations of the memory-transfer micro-benchmark. We used data sizes from 1 Byte to 256 MiB but larger sizes are supported with all approaches. Due to the low variation and long transfer times on M^3 , we only performed 10 runs after 2 warmup runs (instead of 1000 runs after 100 warmup runs). In contrast to RPC, memory transfers are significantly slower on M^3 than with the IPIs+MMU approach. To analyze the reason we performed the same measurement on M^3 with `memcpy` instead of TCU transfers. For larger data sizes, `memcpy` on the FPGA cores is about a factor of two slower than the TCU transfers, whereas small data sizes are faster via `memcpy` due to the overhead to setup TCU transfers. We therefore suspect that the performance gap to the Altra machine is not inherent to the M^3 architecture, but stems from a suboptimal memory architecture in the prototype platform. As expected, the SR-IOV+IOMMU approach performs poorly for small data transfers due to the PCIe latency, but exhibits similar performance as `memcpy` on the Altra machine for larger transfers.

Fig. 7. Read-mostly workload with a key-value store, split into compute time (the same on all systems), time for RPC operations, and time for data transfers.

Fig. 8. Face-verification workload with three different image batch sizes (256 KiB, 512 KiB, and 1024 KiB), split into compute time (the same on all systems), time for RPC operations, and time for data transfers.

6.3. Application-level benchmarks

Finally, we compare the three approaches in more realistic settings. We start with a typical IoT scenario, followed by a scenario found in cloud environments. For the former, we use M³v's key-value store benchmark [21] and replicate the benchmark with the IPIs+MMU and SR-IOV+IOMMU approaches. For the latter, we replicate the face-verification benchmark from FractOS [71] with all three approaches. Since the compute performance is orthogonal to the approach and vastly differs between the platforms, we only replicate the communication and simulate the computation with spinning loops.

6.3.1. IoT scenario

The scenario consists of a client and a server, which both run on the same machine for simplicity. The server hosts leveldb [72] as a key-value store and supports requests to insert, update, and read entries from the key-value store. LevelDB is backed by a file system to store the data. The requests to the server are generated by the Yahoo! Cloud Serving Benchmark (YCSB) [73] and we used a typical read-heavy workload that contains 80% read, 10% insert, and 10% update requests. The workload is generated with the Zipfian distribution and contains 2000 operations, preceded by 200 operations to fill the key-value store.

We run this scenario on M³ with its in-memory file system m3fs and generate a trace that is replayed with the IPIs+MMU and SR-IOV+IOMMU approach. On M³, the client starts by sending a request to the server. The server handles the request, possibly involving multiple memory transfers to the file system. Since the result of the request can be arbitrarily large (the value of a key for the read request), the server writes the result to the client via a memory transfer. Finally, the server responds to the client. The generated trace therefore contains the sent requests and responses as well as the memory transfers. Additionally, the trace contains the compute time that was spent by leveldb (in cycles). This trace is replayed with the two approaches by using the corresponding communication primitive and spinning for the specified number of cycles.

The results in Fig. 7 show the average latency for all performed requests including standard deviation. Like for the memory transfers, we used 10 runs after 2 warmup runs for M³ and 1000 runs after 100 warmup runs on the Altra machine. All bars are split into the time for computation, RPCs, and memory transfers. As can be seen, M³ reaches almost the same performance as MMUs+IPIs despite the

TCU overhead that enables isolation between cores. The number of small RPCs and memory transfers leads to a poor overall latency for the SR-IOV+IOMMU approach, as the micro-benchmarks already indicated.

6.3.2. Cloud scenario

Analogously to the IoT scenario, we now take the benchmark from a system that targets the cloud environments. Namely, we use the face-verification benchmark from FractOS [71] and replicate it with M³, the IPIs+MMU approach, and the SR-IOV+IOMMU approach. FractOS runs this scenario on a disaggregated datacenter with multiple components spread over multiple machines and connected via Infiniband. The benchmarked application offers the ability to verify the identity of a person matching the photo and the ID in the input with the photo corresponding to that ID from a database. The server frontend therefore receives a batch of photos and their IDs from a client. The frontend first obtains access to the photos stored on a SSD from a file system, reads the photos and sends them to the GPU. The GPU performs the face matching algorithm and sends the result back to the frontend, which in turn responds to the client. The communication uses RPC to send requests and responses and a memory transfer to send the photos from the SSD to the GPU. All requests and responses use a payload of 256 bytes and all components run on the same machine, pinned to different cores.

We replicated the components and their communication pattern with all three approaches and used the data sizes and compute times from FractOS. The results in Fig. 8 show the average runtime per batch request, depending on the batch size. We again used 1000 runs with 100 warmup runs on the Altra machine and 10 runs with 2 warmup runs on M³. As can be seen in the figure, for small data sizes, all approaches show similar performance. However, with increasing data sizes M³ exhibits increasing communication overhead. The increased transfer overhead has already been observed in the micro-benchmarks. We suspect that RPC costs are also increased, because the data transfers pollute the cache leading to higher RPC overhead. In general, due to less frequent communication, the SR-IOV+IOMMU approach is more competitive in this scenario than in the IoT scenario.

7. Discussion

After the qualitative and quantitative comparison, we now want to further discuss the results and open questions regarding the feasibility of UCI.

7.1. Evaluation results

The previous section performed a quantitative comparison between the approaches IPIs+MMU, SR-IOV+IOMMU, and M³. At first, the comparison is challenging as they require different hardware platforms, one of them being an FPGA-based research prototype. For that reason, the results have to be interpreted with a grain of salt. However, we still believe that the comparison demonstrates that the UCI requirements can be fulfilled with modest performance costs. Namely, comparing the IPIs+MMU approach (requiring trust into every core) with the M³ approach (not requiring trust into every core) shows that their performance is mostly comparable. We have seen an exception to this in the cloud benchmark, where M³ showed significantly worse performance than the other approaches. But as explained, this seems to be an implementation artifact rather than an inherent disadvantage.

7.2. Hardware costs

Besides the performance implications, adding another per-core hardware component raises the question of its hardware costs. Haas et al. [74] studied the size of the TCU with a synthesized the design based on the Cadence tools by using a 22 nm FDSOI process from Globalfoundries under typical conditions (25 °C, 0.5 V). The design used 100

MHz as the maximum clock frequency to meet all timing requirements under the selected conditions. Haas et al. obtained an area increase of 6% and 10% relatively to the BOOM core and the Rocket core, respectively.

7.3. Scalability

We believe that the UCI model and also the M³ platform can be scaled for different environments and use cases, but each comes with its own challenges. On the one end of the spectrum we have large server machines in datacenters for which we consider UCI to be a good fit. At first, physical attacks can be more easily excluded in datacenters than for IoT devices, for example, which would require additional protection. Adding one or more extra cores for the isolation manager also seems feasible and datacenter provider such as Amazon are already building custom hardware, which make the addition of components like a TCU reachable. However, our current prototype is not built for datacenter environments and thus requires further research to study the implications.

We see larger embedded or IoT devices such as cars, industrial robots, or medical devices in the center of the spectrum and our prototype platform is specifically designed for these use cases. These typically require custom hardware with accelerators to reach the performance and energy-efficiency requirements and thus could also be equipped with additional components like the TCU. Adding a small and simple core such as the in-order Rocket core for the isolation manager seems also feasible and sufficient to manage a small number of application cores. Physical attacks are more difficult to prevent, but opening the SoC that contains all components is significantly more challenging than tapping into off-chip wires.

Finally, there are tiny embedded and IoT devices such as light bulbs or parking-lot sensors which can only afford a single microcontroller for computation. These kind of devices cannot be protected by UCI as it inherently builds upon multiple cores and their isolation from each other.

8. Conclusion

In a world of vulnerabilities in processor cores, isolation implemented by way of these cores restricting their own accesses no longer provides strong security boundaries. With untrusted core isolation (UCI), we present a model to isolate these cores from one another externally, considering enforcement of memory accesses and inter-core signaling, as well as isolation management. From studying architectural candidates, we learned to avoid isolation features built into cores such as MMUs and to run management code outside of untrusted cores. We believe that UCI can establish a new way of thinking about system architecture design by structuring systems according to clean trust relationships between computation and isolation features. Our evaluation of candidate architectures has demonstrated the feasibility of such an approach. Overall system security would benefit from architectures maintaining strong isolation boundaries in the face of arbitrary core vulnerabilities.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Nils Asmussen: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Till Miemietz:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Investigation. **Sebastian Haas:** Writing – review & editing, Software. **Michael Roitzsch:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Project administration, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

We thank Diogo Behrens for his helpful suggestions during the revision. This research is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 101092598 (COREnext) and grant agreement No. 101094218 (CYMED-SEC).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] P. Kocher, D. Genkin, D. Gruss, W. Haas, M. Hamburg, M. Lipp, S. Mangard, T. Prescher, M. Schwarz, Y. Yarom, Spectre attacks: Exploiting speculative execution, 2018, meltdownattack.com. URL: <https://spectreattack.com/spectre.pdf>.
- [2] M. Lipp, M. Schwarz, D. Gruss, T. Prescher, W. Haas, S. Mangard, P. Kocher, D. Genkin, Y. Yarom, M. Hamburg, Meltdown, 2018, meltdownattack.com, URL: <https://meltdownattack.com/meltdown.pdf>.
- [3] P. Borrello, A. Kogler, M. Schwarzl, M. Lipp, D. Gruss, M. Schwarz, *ÆPIC Leak: Architecturally leaking uninitialized data from the microarchitecture*, in: 31st USENIX Security Symposium, 2022.
- [4] M. Schwarz, M. Lipp, D. Moghimi, J.V. Bulck, J. Stecklina, T. Prescher, D. Gruss, *ZombieLoad: Cross-privilege-boundary data sampling*, in: L. Cavallaro, J. Kinder, X. Wang, J. Katz (Eds.), Proceedings of the 2019 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security, CCS 2019, London, UK, November 11–15, 2019, ACM, 2019, pp. 753–768, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/3319535.3354252>.
- [5] J. Van Bulck, M. Minkin, O. Weisse, D. Genkin, B. Kasikci, F. Piessens, M. Silberstein, T.F. Wenisch, Y. Yarom, R. Strackx, *Foreshadow: Extracting the keys to the Intel SGX kingdom with transient out-of-order execution*, in: 27th USENIX Security Symposium, USENIX Security 18, 2018, pp. 991–1008.
- [6] S. van Schaik, A. Milburn, S. Österlund, P. Frigo, G. Maisuradze, K. Razavi, H. Bos, C. Giuffrida, *RIDL: Rogue in-flight data load*, in: S&P, 2019.
- [7] C. Canella, D. Genkin, L. Giner, D. Gruss, M. Lipp, M. Minkin, D. Moghimi, F. Piessens, M. Schwarz, B. Sunar, J. Van Bulck, Y. Yarom, *Fallout: Leaking data on meltdown-resistant CPUs*, in: Proceedings of the ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security, CCS, ACM, 2019.
- [8] J. Van Bulck, D. Moghimi, M. Schwarz, M. Lipp, M. Minkin, D. Genkin, Y. Yuval, B. Sunar, D. Gruss, F. Piessens, *LVI: Hijacking transient execution through microarchitectural load value injection*, in: 41th IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy, S&P'20, 2020.
- [9] J. Stecklina, T. Prescher, *LazyFP: Leaking FPU register state using microarchitectural side-channels*, 2018, arXiv preprint [arXiv:1806.07480](https://arxiv.org/abs/1806.07480).
- [10] J. Wikner, K. Razavi, *RETBLEED: Arbitrary speculative code execution with return instructions*, in: 31st USENIX Security Symposium, USENIX Security 22, 2022, pp. 3825–3842.
- [11] R. McIlroy, J. Sevcik, T. Tebbi, B.L. Titzer, T. Verwaest, *Spectre is here to stay: An analysis of side-channels and speculative execution*, 2019, URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1902.05178v1>.
- [12] S32G2 processors for vehicle networking, 2022, <https://www.nxp.com/products/processors-and-microcontrollers/s32-automotive-platform/s32g-vehicle-network-processors/s32g2-processors-for-vehicle-networking:S32G2>. (Accessed 8 August 2022).
- [13] R-car-S4: Automotive system-on-chip (SoC) for car server/communication gateway, 2022, <https://www.renesas.com/us/en/products/automotive-products/automotive-system-chips-socs/r-car-s4-automotive-system-chip-soc-car-servercommunication-gateway>. (Accessed 8 August 2022).
- [14] O. Oleksenko, B. Trach, R. Krahn, M. Silberstein, C. Fetzer, *Varys: Protecting SGX enclaves from practical Side-Channel attacks*, in: 2018 USENIX Annual Technical Conference, USENIX ATC 18, 2018, pp. 227–240.
- [15] P. Turner, *Retpoline: a software construct for preventing branch-target-injection*, 2022, <https://support.google.com/faqs/answer/7625886>. (Accessed on 21 November 2022).
- [16] D. Gruss, M. Lipp, M. Schwarz, R. Fellner, C. Maurice, S. Mangard, *KASLR is dead: long live KASLR*, in: International Symposium on Engineering Secure Software and Systems, Springer, 2017, pp. 161–176.
- [17] Apple, Inc., *Secure Enclave*, in: Apple Platform Security, Spring 2020, p. 8, https://manuals.info.apple.com/MANUALS/1000/MA1902/en_US/apple-platform-security-guide.pdf.
- [18] Advanced Micro Devices, Inc., *Platform Security Processor (PSP)*, in: BIOS and Kernel Developer's Guide (BKDG) for AMD Family 16h Models 30h-3Fh Processors, 2016, pp. 156–157, https://www.amd.com/system/files/TechDocs/52740_16h_Models_30h-3Fh_BKDG.pdf.

- [19] N. Asmussen, M. Völpl, B. Nöthen, H. Härtig, G. Fettweis, M3: A hardware/operating-system co-design to tame heterogeneous manycores, in: 21st International Conference on Architectural Support for Programming Languages and Operating Systems, ASPLOS, ACM, 2016, pp. 189–203, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/2872362.2872371>.
- [20] N. Asmussen, M. Roitzsch, H. Härtig, M³: Autonomous accelerators via context-enabled fast-path communication, in: USENIX Annual Technical Conference, ATC, USENIX, 2019, pp. 617–632.
- [21] N. Asmussen, S. Haas, C. Weinhold, T. Miemietz, M. Roitzsch, Efficient and scalable core multiplexing with M³v, in: 27th ACM International Conference on Architectural Support for Programming Languages and Operating Systems, ASPLOS, ACM, 2022, pp. 452–466, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/3503222.3507741>.
- [22] N. Asmussen, S. Haas, A. Lackorzynski, M. Roitzsch, Core-local reasoning and predictable cross-core communication with M³, in: 2024 IEEE 30th Real-Time and Embedded Technology and Applications Symposium, RTAS, IEEE, 2024, pp. 199–211.
- [23] D.J. Bernstein, Cache-timing attacks on AES, <https://cr.yp.to/antiforgery/cachetiming-20050414.pdf>.
- [24] D.A. Osvik, A. Shamir, E. Tromer, Cache attacks and countermeasures: The case of AES, in: Topics in Cryptology – CT-RSA 2006, Springer, 2006, URL: <https://eprint.iacr.org/2005/271.pdf>.
- [25] C. Percival, Cache missing for fun and profit, <https://www.daemonology.net/papers/htt.pdf>.
- [26] A. Prout, W. Arcand, D. Bestor, B. Bergeron, C. Byun, V. Gadepally, M. Houle, M. Hubbell, M. Jones, A. Klein, P. Michaleas, L. Milechin, J. Mullen, A. Rosa, S. Samsi, C. Yee, A. Reuther, J. Kepner, Measuring the impact of Spectre and Meltdown, in: 2018 IEEE High Performance Extreme Computing Conference, HPEC 2018, Waltham, MA, USA, September 25–27, 2018, IEEE, 2018, pp. 1–5, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/HPEC.2018.8547554>.
- [27] G. Dessouky, D. Gens, P. Haney, G. Persyn, A. Kanuparthi, H. Khattri, J.M. Fung, A.-R. Sadeghi, J. Rajendran, Hardfals: Insights into software-exploitable hardware bugs, in: 28th USENIX Conference on Security Symposium, SEC, USENIX, 2019, pp. 213–230.
- [28] A. Baumann, Hardware is the new software, in: 16th Workshop on Hot Topics in Operating Systems, HotOS, ACM, 2017, pp. 132–137, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/3102980.3103002>.
- [29] F. Thomas, L. Hetterich, R. Zhang, D. Weber, L. Gerlach, M. Schwarz, RISCvuzz: Discovering architectural CPU vulnerabilities via differential hardware fuzzing, 2024, <https://ghostwritetattack.com/>.
- [30] R. Dennard, V. Rideout, E. Bassous, A. LeBlanc, Design of ion-implanted MOSFET's with very small physical dimensions, IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits 9 (5) (1974) 256–268, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/JSSC.1974.1050511>.
- [31] G. Klein, K. Elphinstone, G. Heiser, J. Andronick, D. Cock, P. Derrin, D. Elkaduwe, K. Engelhardt, K. Kolanski, M. Norrish, T. Sewell, H. Tuch, S. Winwood, seL4: Formal verification of an OS kernel, in: Proceedings of the ACM SIGOPS 22nd Symposium on Operating Systems Principles, SOSP '09, ACM, New York, NY, USA, 2009, pp. 207–220, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/1629575.1629596>, URL: <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/1629575.1629596>.
- [32] A. Lackorzynski, A. Warg, Taming subsystems: Capabilities as universal resource access control in L4, in: Proceedings of the Second Workshop on Isolation and Integration in Embedded Systems, IIES '09, ACM, New York, NY, USA, 2009, pp. 25–30, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/1519130.1519135>, URL: <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/1519130.1519135>.
- [33] U. Steinberg, B. Kauer, NOVA: a microhypervisor-based secure virtualization architecture, in: C. Morin, G. Muller (Eds.), European Conference on Computer Systems, Proceedings of the 5th European Conference on Computer Systems, EuroSys 2010, Paris, France, April 13–16, 2010, ACM, 2010, pp. 209–222, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/1755913.1755935>.
- [34] S. Biggs, D. Lee, G. Heiser, The jury is in: Monolithic OS design is flawed: Microkernel-based designs improve security, in: Proceedings of the 9th Asia-Pacific Workshop on Systems, APSys 2018, Jeju Island, Republic of Korea, August 27–28, 2018, ACM, 2018, pp. 16:1–16:7, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/3265723.3265733>.
- [35] AMD SEV-SNP: Strengthening VM Isolation With Integrity Protection and More, AMD, 2020, <https://www.amd.com/system/files/TechDocs/SEV-SNP-strengthening-vm-isolation-with-integrity-protection-and-more.pdf>. (Accessed on 8 November 2022).
- [36] K. Murdock, D.F. Oswald, F.D. Garcia, J.V. Bulck, D. Gruss, F. Piessens, Plundervolt: Software-based fault injection attacks against intel SGX, in: 2020 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy, SP 2020, San Francisco, CA, USA, May 18–21, 2020, IEEE, 2020, pp. 1466–1482, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/SP40000.2020.00057>.
- [37] A. Tang, S. Sethumadhavan, S.J. Stolfo, CLKSCREW: exposing the perils of security-oblivious energy management, in: E. Kirda, T. Ristenpart (Eds.), 26th USENIX Security Symposium, USENIX Security 2017, Vancouver, BC, Canada, August 16–18, 2017, USENIX Association, 2017, pp. 1057–1074, URL: <https://www.usenix.org/conference/usenixsecurity17/technical-sessions/presentation/tang>.
- [38] Y. Kim, R. Daly, J. Kim, C. Fallin, J.H. Lee, D. Lee, C. Wilkerson, K. Lai, O. Mutlu, Flipping bits in memory without accessing them: An experimental study of DRAM disturbance errors, in: 41st International Symposium on Computer Architecture, ISCA, IEEE, 2014.
- [39] M. Schwarz, M. Schwarzl, M. Lipp, J. Masters, D. Gruss, NetSpectre: Read arbitrary memory over network, in: K. Sako, S.A. Schneider, P.Y.A. Ryan (Eds.), Computer Security - ESORICS 2019 - 24th European Symposium on Research in Computer Security, Luxembourg, September 23–27, 2019, Proceedings, Part I, in: Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 11735, Springer, 2019, pp. 279–299, http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-29959-0_14.
- [40] Q. Ge, Y. Yarom, T. Chothia, G. Heiser, Time protection: the missing OS abstraction, in: Proceedings of the Fourteenth EuroSys Conference 2019, 2019, pp. 1–17.
- [41] A. Baumann, P. Barham, P.-E. Dagand, T. Harris, R. Isaacs, S. Peter, T. Roscoe, A. Schüpbach, A. Singhanian, The multikernel: A new OS architecture for scalable multicore systems, in: Proceedings of the ACM SIGOPS 22nd Symposium on Operating Systems Principles, SOSP '09, ACM, New York, NY, USA, 2009, pp. 29–44, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/1629575.1629579>, URL: <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/1629575.1629579>.
- [42] B. Nitzberg, V. Lo, Distributed shared memory: A survey of issues and algorithms, Computer 24 (8) (1991) 52–60.
- [43] AWS Nitro System, Amazon Web Services, 2022, <https://aws.amazon.com/de/ec2/nitro/>. (Accessed on 14 November 2022).
- [44] D. Firestone, A. Putnam, S. Mundkur, D. Chiou, A. Dabagh, M. Andrewartha, H. Angepat, V. Bhanu, A. Caulfield, E. Chung, et al., Azure accelerated networking: SmartNICs in the public cloud, in: 15th USENIX Symposium on Networked Systems Design and Implementation, NSDI, USENIX, 2018, pp. 51–66.
- [45] D. Wentzlaff, P. Griffin, H. Hoffmann, L. Bao, B. Edwards, C. Ramey, M. Mattina, C.-C. Miao, J.F. Brown III, A. Agarwal, On-chip interconnection architecture of the tile processor, IEEE Micro 27 (2007) 15–31, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/MM.2007.89>, URL: doi.ieeeecomputersociety.org/10.1109/MM.2007.89.
- [46] J. Liedtke, On micro-kernel construction, in: Proceedings of the Fifteenth ACM Symposium on Operating Systems Principles, SOSP '95, ACM, New York, NY, USA, 1995, pp. 237–250, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/224056.224075>, URL: <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/224056.224075>.
- [47] Y.-S. Won, J.-Y. Park, D.-G. Han, S. Bhasin, Practical cold boot attack on iot device-case study on raspberry pi, in: 2020 IEEE International Symposium on the Physical and Failure Analysis of Integrated Circuits, IPFA, IEEE, 2020, pp. 1–4.
- [48] S. Charles, Y. Lyu, P. Mishra, Real-time detection and localization of distributed DoS attacks in NoC-based SoCs, IEEE Trans. Comput.-Aided Des. Integr. Circuits Syst. 39 (12) (2020) 4510–4523.
- [49] A. Savino, G. Gala, M. Cinque, G. Fohrer, Multicore DRAM bank-& row-conflict bomb for timing attacks in mixed-criticality systems, in: 2024 IEEE 27th International Symposium on Real-Time Distributed Computing, ISORC, IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–10.
- [50] U. Ali, O. Khan, [Connoc]: A practical timing channel attack on network-on-chip hardware in a multicore processor, in: 2021 IEEE International Symposium on Hardware Oriented Security and Trust, HOST, IEEE, 2021, pp. 192–202.
- [51] V. van der Veen, B. Gras, DramaQueen: Revisiting Side Channels in DRAM, DRAMSec, 2023.
- [52] CVE-2024-42314, 2024, <https://www.cve.org/CVERecord?id=CVE-2024-42314>. Viewed 28 August 2024.
- [53] CVE-2024-4761, 2024, <https://www.cve.org/CVERecord?id=CVE-2024-4761>. Viewed 28 August 2024.
- [54] M. Fährdrich, M. Aiken, C. Hawblitzel, O. Hodson, G. Hunt, J.R. Larus, S. Levi, Language support for fast and reliable message-based communication in Singularity OS, in: Proceedings of the 1st ACM SIGOPS/EuroSys European Conference on Computer Systems, EuroSys '06, ACM, New York, NY, USA, 2006, pp. 177–190, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/1217935.1217953>, URL: <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/1217935.1217953>.
- [55] J. Porquet, A. Greiner, C. Schwarz, NoC-MPU: A secure architecture for flexible co-hosting on shared memory MPSoCs, in: Design, Automation and Test in Europe, DATE 2011, Grenoble, France, March 14–18, 2011, IEEE, 2011, pp. 591–594, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/DATE.2011.5763291>.
- [56] L. Fiorin, G. Palermo, S. Lukovic, V. Catalano, C. Silvano, Secure memory accesses on networks-on-chip, IEEE Trans. Comput. 57 (9) (2008) 1216–1229, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TC.2008.69>.
- [57] J. Woodruff, R.N. Watson, D. Chisnall, S.W. Moore, J. Anderson, B. Davis, B. Laurie, P.G. Neumann, R. Norton, M. Roe, The CHERI capability model: Revisiting RISC in an age of risk, in: Proceeding of the 41st Annual International Symposium on Computer Architecture, ISCA '14, IEEE Press, Piscataway, NJ, USA, 2014, pp. 457–468, URL: <http://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=2665671.2665740>.
- [58] Trustzone for Cortex A – TEE Reference Documentation, ARM Technology, 2021, <https://www.arm.com/why-arm/technologies/trustzone-for-cortex-a/tee-reference-documentation>. (Accessed on 23 January 2021).
- [59] Intel Software Guard Extensions (Intel SGX), Intel Corporation, 2021, <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/architecture-and-technology/software-guard-extensions.html>. (Accessed on 23 January 2021).

- [60] Intel Trust Domain Extensions, Intel Corporation, 2020, <https://software.intel.com/content/dam/develop/external/us/en/documents/tdxwhitepaper-v4.pdf>. (Accessed on 8 November 2022).
- [61] V. Costan, I. Lebedev, S. Devadas, Sanctum: Minimal hardware extensions for strong software isolation, in: 25th USENIX Security Symposium, USENIX Security 16, 2016, pp. 857–874.
- [62] J. Noorman, P. Agten, W. Daniels, R. Strackx, A.V. Herrewewege, C. Huygens, B. Preneel, I. Verbauwhede, F. Piessens, Sancus: Low-cost trustworthy extensible networked devices with a zero-software trusted computing base, in: S.T. King (Ed.), Proceedings of the 22th USENIX Security Symposium, Washington, DC, USA, August 14–16, 2013, USENIX Association, 2013, pp. 479–494, URL: <https://www.usenix.org/conference/usenixsecurity13/technical-sessions/presentation/noorman>.
- [63] H. Zhang, S. Ghosh, J. Fix, S. Apostolakis, S.R. Beard, N.P. Nagendra, T. Oh, D.I. August, Architectural support for containment-based security, in: 24th International Conference on Architectural Support for Programming Languages and Operating Systems, ASPLOS, 2019, pp. 361–377.
- [64] D. Cock, A. Ramdas, D. Schwyn, M. Giardino, A. Turowski, Z. He, N. Hossle, D. Korolija, M. Licciardello, K. Martsenko, et al., Enzian: an open, general, CPU/FPGA platform for systems software research, in: Proceedings of the 27th ACM International Conference on Architectural Support for Programming Languages and Operating Systems, 2022, pp. 434–451.
- [65] J. Balkind, M. McKeown, Y. Fu, T. Nguyen, Y. Zhou, A. Lavrov, M. Shahrad, A. Fuchs, S. Payne, X. Liang, et al., OpenPiton: An open source manycore research framework, ACM SIGPLAN Notices 51 (4) (2016) 217–232.
- [66] J. Balkind, K. Lim, M. Schaffner, F. Gao, G. Chirkov, A. Li, A. Lavrov, T.M. Nguyen, Y. Fu, F. Zaruba, et al., BYOC: a “bring your own core” framework for heterogeneous-ISA research, in: Proceedings of the Twenty-Fifth International Conference on Architectural Support for Programming Languages and Operating Systems, 2020, pp. 699–714.
- [67] Z. Zhou, Y. Shan, W. Cui, X. Ge, M. Peinado, A. Baumann, Core slicing: closing the gap between leaky confidential VMs and baremetal cloud, in: Proceedings of the 17th Symposium on Operating System Design and Implementation, OSDI, 2023.
- [68] Microkernel-based system for heterogeneous manycores, 2023, <https://github.com/Barkhausen-Institut/M3>. Viewed 4 December 2023.
- [69] K. Asanović, R. Avizienis, J. Bachrach, S. Beamer, D. Biancolin, C. Celio, H. Cook, D. Dabbelt, J. Hauser, A. Izraelevitz, S. Karandikar, B. Keller, D. Kim, J. Koenig, The Rocket Chip Generator, Tech. Rep. UCB/EECS-2016-17, EECS Department, University of California, Berkeley, 2016.
- [70] J. Zhao, B. Korpan, A. Gonzalez, K. Asanovic, SonicBOOM: The 3rd generation berkeley out-of-order machine, in: Fourth Workshop on Computer Architecture Research with RISC-V, 2020.
- [71] L. Vilanova, L. Maudlej, S. Bergman, T. Miemietz, M. Hille, N. Asmussen, M. Roitzsch, H. Härtig, M. Silberstein, Slashing the disaggregation tax in heterogeneous data centers with FractOS, in: European Conference on Computer Systems, EuroSys, Rennes, France, 2022, pp. 352–367, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/3492321.3519569>.
- [72] google/leveldb, 2021, <https://github.com/google/leveldb>. (Accessed on 11 August 2021).
- [73] brianfrankcooper/YCSB: Yahoo! Cloud serving benchmark, 2021, <https://ycsb.site/>. (Accessed on 11 August 2021).
- [74] S. Haas, N. Asmussen, A trusted communication unit for secure tiled hardware architectures, in: 2022 29th IEEE International Conference on Electronics, Circuits, and Systems, ICECS, 2022, pp. 1–4.

Nils Asmussen received his Ph.D. at Technische Universität Dresden under Prof. Hermann Härtig. Nils introduced the M³ architecture with his Ph.D. thesis, which initially focussed on heterogeneous systems. Since 2019 he works as a principal researcher at the Barkhausen Institut gGmbH in Dresden where the work on the M³ system architecture is continued based on a larger team of OS and hardware researchers. His research interests include the boundary between hardware and software, programming languages, and microkernel-based systems.

Till Miemietz received his Dipl.-Inf. degree in Computer Science in 2020 from Technische Universität Dresden, Germany. Afterwards, he joined the Composable Operating Systems research group at Barkhausen Institut gGmbH in Dresden to pursue his doctoral studies. Till’s research activities focus on leveraging the benefits of microkernel-based operating systems in data-center settings.

Sebastian Haas received his Dipl.-Ing. (M.Sc.) degree in Electrical Engineering in 2013 and his Dr.-Ing. (Ph.D.) in 2019 both from Technische Universität Dresden, Germany. From 2013 to 2019 he has been with the Vodafone Chair at Technische Universität Dresden, where he was working in the hardware design group. Currently he is a research associate at Barkhausen Institut gGmbH, Dresden, Germany. His research interests include secure and energy-efficient hardware architectures in Multiprocessor System-on-Chips for the Internet of Things.

Michael Roitzsch received his Ph.D. at Technische Universität Dresden under Prof. Hermann Härtig. His earlier works focussed on real-time scheduling within application runtimes. In 2019 he became leader of the Composable Operating Systems group at Barkhausen Institute. The group works on microkernels and hardware-software co-designs to improve trustworthiness in the Internet of Things.